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Challenges of modern education as a threat to national, regional and global security

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Modern education in most countries and regions of the world, at all its levels, unfortunately, does not meet the needs and requirements of the time. The current global world is changing so rapidly technically, communicatively, mentally that no educational reforms simply can keep up with it. Any institution, any transformation is very late. As a result, education does not meet the requirements of the times. In fact, today's schools, colleges, universities train specialists who, after receiving diplomas, for the most part will not be in demand. This creates a range of security threats at various levels. Firstly, it contributes to the actualization of threats to economic security, since one way or another contributes to the emergence of economic crises. Secondly, an increase in the number of people who have not found a place for themselves in the social system will contribute to the actualization of the problems and threats of transnational crime and international terrorism. The increase in the gap between the education system and the real world will contribute to a decrease in the level of culture, including the political one. As a result, an increase in the likelihood of new hotbeds of tension, local and regional conflicts. It is necessary to change conceptual approaches to education, changing and even completely abolishing educational standards, canons and bringing education to a new super-technological and qualitative level.

Keywords: Actualization, Economic, Transnational, Conflicts, Super-technology

Introduction

Modern education in most countries and regions of the world, at all its levels, unfortunately, does not meet the needs and requirements of the time. The current global world is changing so rapidly technically, communicatively, mentally that no educational reforms simply can keep up with it. Any institution, any transformation is very late. As a result, education does not meet the requirements of the times. In fact, today's schools, colleges, universities train specialists who, after receiving diplomas, for the most part will not be in

demand. This creates a range of security threats at various levels. Firstly, it contributes to the actualization of threats to economic security, since one way or another contributes to the emergence of economic crises. Secondly, an increase in the number of people who have not found a place for themselves in the social system will contribute to the actualization of the problems and threats of transnational crime and international terrorism. The increase in the gap between the education system and the real world will contribute

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to a decrease in the level of culture, including the political one. As a result, an increase in the likelihood of new hotbeds of tension, local and regional conflicts. It is necessary to change conceptual approaches to education, changing and even completely abolishing educational standards, canons and bringing education to a new super-technological and qualitative level. The problem of modern education as a threat to security, of course, has several levels and scales.

First, this is a problem at the level of individual states. Moreover, it is not only in some specific countries. She is everywhere. In the context of the development of education, the acceleration of technological progress, the interdependence of all from all, the interpenetration and intersection of scientific disciplines and directions, education cannot cope with the requirements of the time. The accepted training programs, standards, sets of knowledge and skills, after 4 years of study at the university, become so outdated that no one needs them anymore. The gap between learning, theory, practice and specific conditional production has increased so much that it really became a threat to the further stable existence of society.

Attempts by individual Western universities to give the opportunity to freely visit, choose a set of disciplines for students during the learning process, also do not bring any results. Since universities are simply physically unable to rebuild so quickly.

At the national level, this threatens with an economic crisis in a number of sectors of the national economy - in the production of new technologies, new sectors of services and vitality, "green economy", etc. And as a result - a decrease in the standard of living of the population, the ruin of small and medium-sized businesses, a decrease in purchasing power, erosion and a decrease in the number of the so-called "middle class".

Secondly, this is the level, which we will conditionally denote by the well-known theoretical, Eurocentric construction "Core-periphery". Threats of an education crisis will hit not only the developed countries of the West, but also the countries of Africa, Asia, South and Latin America. In addition, if TNCs, large Western companies to relatively adapt to the situation. Then in countries that have not so strong and developed economies, the crisis will be much more serious and tangible. The level of degradation of the education system will be seriously correlated with an increase in the level of threats associated with the activities of transnational criminal groups, international drug trafficking, human trafficking, as well as with the actualization of the problems of international terrorism.

Thirdly, this is a global level. At this level, we will fall into the so-called "bad students" trap. The discrepancy between the level of education, the level of preparedness of the new adult generation of people, the new technically developed world, leads to very serious threats, security challenges. Many threats simply can even be misunderstood, unconscious, and the very fact of a global catastrophe can be extremely unexpected.

The development of artificial intelligence, biotechnology, anthropomorphic robots - these are no longer words from science fiction novels, and not the near future. Now it is real. However, high-quality education that meets the spirit of the times is only a desirable and yet unrealizable aspiration.

In the very near future, a significant transformation of education is required, it is necessary to invest money not only in scientific developments, but also in comparable amounts in the development of educational problems. It is quite possible that in the very near future, education in the form in which it exists today will simply cease to exist (as unnecessary, lack of practical meaning and inability to keep up with the times).

In fact, there is a very old, moral or even moral-philosophical problem - this is a discrepancy between the level of development of human morality and morality, and the technological level that society reaches. And every year this gap grows even more. And today, this problem is also superimposed by the crisis of education, the threats emanating from its inconsistency with the requirements of the times. And these two dilemmas are very close.